

UBONGO Flow Game

Developed by: Jan Fischbach, using Gregorz Rejchtman's Ubongo Game

(Publisher: KOSMOS Verlag)

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Keywords

Agile Project Management, Process Optimization, Project Management, Teamwork, Workflow Simulation

Figure 1. Photo of the UBONGO Flow Game setup (Jan Fischbach; KOSMOS Verlag). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

Introduction

The *UBONGO Flow Game* (see Figure 1) is based on the classic UBONGO Game, in which players quickly place geometric shapes on a board, similarly to Tangrams. The first player to fit the correct pieces into the given space on the board wins.

The UBONGO Flow Game is an analog serious game with a learning focus that uses materials from the original game. The only adopted element is the mechanism of placing pieces on a

mold. However, the participants work together in teams with distributed roles and have an extended task (work packages) to be completed.

The game simulates the effects of process changes on results. Project work across several workstations is further developed over three rounds, gradually optimizing processes to create a more agile and open system. It is for high school students aged 14 and over, university students, and corporate training. The design is characterized by clear role definitions and continuous optimization in each round. Participants recognize the significance of effective collaboration on outcomes. It is based on the LEGO® Flow Game, developed by Karl Scotland and Sallyann Freudenberg in 2014, and refined by Jan Fischbach in 2016.

Facts

Release date:	October 2016 (German version), July 2019 (English version), based on the LEGO® Flow Game (May 2014)
Developer:	Jan Fischbach, use of Grzegorz Rejchtman's Ubongo Game (Publisher: KOSMOS Verlag)
Game type:	Analog
Number of players:	4–8 players per set, optimum of 6 players
Format:	Synchronous
Time frame:	The total duration is about 90 minutes; 3 rounds of 6 min each, plus in-between debriefings and a final debriefing session.
Languages:	English, German
Environment:	Each team needs a table (about 1.4 m x 1.4 m) with places for each team member, no digital requirements
Material:	One set of the UBONGO! Classic game per team, plus a set of cards and poster templates
Price:	The cost of the UBONGO! Classic Game is about 25 Euro, additional material (Specification and Role cards) for free, if applicable, post-it notes, and a flipchart for the result slide

Resonance & Criticism

At present, no official user figures for the game are available. Given that the material is available as open source in addition to the purchase of the game, which is available in every toy shop, it can be assumed that the game is spreading through experience in use. An extensive website (Fischbach, J., 2019) with downloadable material is available. It has not yet received any awards.

The participants had a good flow during our sessions; there were strong emotions, especially during competition between several teams, and the feedback after playing the game was consistently positive. The game mechanics are well-balanced, ensuring the desired effects and results are achieved.

Game Principle & Process

The UBONGO Flow Game enables participants to experience processes and organizational models interactively in a short time, making the advantages and disadvantages of classic versus multifunctional/open team structures directly noticeable and available for reflection (Buntrock et al., 2019).

Each team receives role cards with a specific task, for example, sponsors who select work packages, which are passed to the analyst, who selects the puzzle board. The supplier delivers the parts. The developer covers the board with the parts that fit the mold. The test manager checks that everything is correct and reports to the facilitators. An observer and/or scribe can be included (Fischbach, 2019).

The game is played in three six-minute rounds with interim debriefings. The goals and rules for each round are clear, but they change from one round to the next. The production structures are rigid, and it is hard to reach the goal in the first round, but more flexibility is added to improve the processes.

After 2 or 3 minutes, there is time for one or two interim debriefings where the team reflects on their collaboration. When multiple teams are engaged, the objective is to accrue the most points possible after three rounds. Participants become emotionally engaged, experiencing impatience and stress. It is crucial to provide space for the expression of these intense emotions during the debriefing, ensuring that reasons for initial goal failures are thoroughly discussed (Buntrock et al, 2019).

In the contemporary business world, agility has become vital to effective project management. Its ability to enhance responsiveness to changes and uncertainties in a dynamic business environment has been shown to lead to more successful project outcomes (Stare, 2013). Agile methodologies enable teams to adapt to today's fast-paced environment, improving project efficiency in organizations.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

In the game, players experience three distinct workflows that introduce them to various project management approaches: Waterfall, Kanban, and Scrum. This immersive setup enables players to compare the efficiency, flexibility, and collaborative dynamics of traditional and agile methods. For more on these process models, see Gaborov et al. (2021). A key takeaway from the game is the significant impact of process design: how a team works together can influence outcomes more than individual skills or motivation.

Workflows and bottlenecks are made tangible through puzzle boards representing work packages. This allows players to observe how tasks move through the system and identify points of delay or inefficiency. Each participant assumes a specific role, such as analyst, developer, or manager, thereby fostering role-based collaboration and enhancing team communication.

Value creation is measured through points earned for completed work packages, giving teams a way to gauge their productivity and consider how different approaches influence their results. After each round, teams discuss their experiences, promoting a culture of iterative learning and continuous improvement.

By making abstract agile principles concrete and experiential, the game helps players to better understand and apply these concepts to real-world projects (Fischbach, 2019). Ultimately, it challenges teams to tackle a complex task that requires thoughtful optimization, thereby reinforcing the importance of adaptive processes and collaborative problem-solving. Therefore, the UBONGO Flow Game can be used to achieve a broad range of learning objectives for participants.

Regarding the role of the facilitator, effective learning outcomes are achieved when they create a conducive learning atmosphere by clearly defining the rules in the briefing, accompanying the game phase with an appropriate mix of active and restrained involvement, and asking suitable questions during the debriefing. Preparation by the facilitators involves a thorough study of the game documents and, if possible, a trial run, and can be completed in about a day. Due to clear objectives and possibly a competitive environment with other teams, the participants are highly engaged in the event and experience strong emotional responses, which promote the achievement of the learning objectives.

Effectiveness

Regrettably, there is a lack of studies or scientific evidence supporting this game's effectiveness. However, participants have reported high enjoyment levels, citing insights into various process models. Additionally, the optimization discussions have motivated them to engage.

The development – from initial high stress and frustration to peak productivity – is an immersive learning experience. The participants reported back: "I would never have thought it possible that we would improve so much!" or "The effect of small adjustments is amazing!"

The debriefing after each round follows a four-step recommendation. First, emotions are collected: How are you feeling? Who was stressed, who was bored, or who became frustrated because the process took too long? Next, the managers report on what happened, how they proceeded, and where they noticed weaknesses. This is followed by a joint reflection on possible solutions based on these experiences. In the final step, the innovations and rules for the next game phase are presented; after the last round, this step becomes an open discussion in which parallels to real situations are identified and the overall picture is brought together.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

The game focuses on process optimization and does not promote discrimination or other insensitive behavior. However, the time and social pressure experienced by players in

bottleneck roles are deliberate design features. Role owners can feel stressed even when players act calmly. The game allows players to swap roles, and those in 'stressful' roles often want to swap with someone else, which helps with social pressure. Players in these roles do not require warnings about the pressure. The pressure encourages ideas for preventing it. These issues are discussed during team debriefings to develop solutions. The facilitator should only intervene if the behavior becomes accusatory or aggressive. The information provided is invaluable and is suitable for all target groups.

Reviewer(s): Tim Rogmans, Elizabeth Peacock

Sources

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